

A review of the antimalarial and antidiabetic potential of *Moringa oleifera*

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Abstract

Moringa oleifera, also called drumstick tree is one of the most commonly used traditional plant with several pharmacological characteristics such as antimalarial, antidiabetic, antipyretic, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, wound healing, anti-microbial, antidiarrheal, analgesic, cardiovascular, nootropic, immunomodulatory, anti-asthmatic, diuretic, anti-ulcer, antiepileptic, anti-allergic, hepatoprotective, gastroprotective and anti-obesity activities. This review focus on a comprehensive summary of the antimalarial and antidiabetic potential of *Moringa oleifera*. In addition, it will focus on the relationship between malarial and diabetes. I think it is an interesting topic for further experimental and clinical investigations.

Keywords: anti-diabetic, antimalarial, phytochemical, *Moringa oleifera*.

Introduction

Especially in sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America, and Asia, malaria is a serious parasite illness with high fatality and morbidity rates. Worldwide, 3 billion individuals are exposed to malaria every year, of whom 1.2 billion are at high risk and 200 million have developed symptoms. Additionally, it was projected that 1 million people died worldwide (White et al., 2014). At the same time, type 2 diabetes mellitus is increasing at the greatest rate in the world in sub-Saharan Africa; adaptation to Western lifestyles and genetic predispositions may quicken this trend (Wild et al., 2004). Urban Ghana has a 6.3 percent prevalence of type 2 diabetes mellitus ten years ago (Amoah et al., 2002). There may be 20 million affected people living in sub-Saharan Africa by 2030. (Wild et al., 2004). Common infections are more likely to develop in people with type 2 diabetes (Muller et al., 2005). The increasing co-occurrence of type 2 diabetes mellitus with tropical infectious illnesses in Sub-Saharan Africa may therefore have significant consequences. Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus had a 46 percent higher chance of contracting *Plasmodium falciparum* infection, according to a case-control study of 1,466 urban adults in Ghana (Danquah et al., 2010). More people may be at risk for contracting malaria if the frequency of diabetes mellitus rises.

Figure 2: Topographical distribution of *M. oleifera*

Moringa oleifera (MO), also called drumstick shown in figure 1, is indigenous to West Africa specifically Ghana and Nigeria, *Moringa oleifera* (MO), also known as the drumstick tree, has since been grown and naturalized in a number of other nations, including Afghanistan, Nepal, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, South and Central America, the West Indies, the Philippines, and Cambodia (Durgesh et al., 2013). Numerous pharmacological studies have demonstrated that this plant has a variety of beneficial properties, including those that are analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, anticancer, antioxidant, nootropic, hepatoprotective, gastroprotective, anti-ulcer, cardiovascular, anti-obesity, antiepileptic, anti-asthmatic, anti-urolithiatic,

diuretic, local anesthetic, anti-allergic, and anthelmintic activities (Kumar et al., 2018). These large number of pharmacological properties result from the presence of several phytochemicals such as saponin alkaloid, flavonoids, tannins, cardiac glycosides, steroids, polyphenols and other phytoconstituents. Analysis has shown that the percentages of phytochemicals are not toxic, meaning they may not be harmful or fatal (Reminus and Walter, 2019). This has also demonstrated the usefulness of *Moringa oleifera* for maintaining excellent health and the fact that some sections are highly palatable and digestible (Verkaik, 2006). According to Gupta et al. (2014), the presence of saponin, flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, alkaloids terpenoids and steroids are responsible for wound healing, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, immunomodulatory, antimalarial and antioxidant properties in MO. This review focuses on the antimalarial and antidiabetic potential of MO as well how malaria is related diabetes activity.

Figure 1: *Moringa oleifera*

Method

Sources for this review are mainly obtained from articles, dissertation and theses via online databases such as Science direct, Google scholar, PubMed, Elsevier, Researchgate, and Frontiers as well as medicinal chemistry books from Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology library. Accurate references are given to all sources used in this paper.

Phytochemistry

Using the usual approach outlined by Evans (1999), experiments were carried out for the screening and identification of eight phytoconstituents contained in the *Moringa oleifera* by Nishu and Chandrawati Jee (2020). The investigation was conducted in methanol, ethanol, and petroleum ether extracts. The main compounds to be studied are the active phytochemical compounds, which include tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids, steroids, terpenoids, saponins, glycosides, and polyphenols. The findings are reported in table 1. Alkaloids, saponins, polyphenol, tannins, glycosides, flavanoids, and terpenoids all displayed a variety of outcomes

in the screening process using various solvent extracts. Alkaloids, steroids, glycosides, polyphenols, and tannin were found in all three solvents during this phytochemical screening. Terpenoids and saponin were not present in the petroleum ether solvent, but flavanoids were not present in the methanol solvent.

Phyto- Chemicals	Methanol	Ethanol	Petroleum Ether
Alkaloids	+	+	+
Flavonoids	-	+	+
Glycosides	+	+	+
Steroids	+	+	+
Polyphenol	+	+	+
Terpenoides	+	+	-
Saponins	+	+	-
tannin	+	+	+

(Nishu and Chandrawati Jee , 2020).

Antimalarial activity of *Moringa oleifera*

A study carried out by Kondee et al. (2016), on ICR mice experimentally infected with *Plasmodium bergi* showed a remarkable potent suppressive and curative activities. This was as a result of presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, quercetin and kaempferol (Vongsak et al., 2014). Additionally, a research work conducted by Somsak et al. (2016), proved that MO leaves in combination with artesunate presented a higher of suppression on the malaria parasites compared to the individual extract. By measuring the percentage of parasitemia development that was inhibited, *M. oleifera* leaves demonstrated potent antimalarial effects in a dose-dependent manner against *P. berghei* infection in mice (Somasak et al., 2016). A dose-dependent response was shown by the leaf extract. The antimalarial activity considerably increased with increasing dose. Various types of active substances, including tannins, alkaloids, quinines, saponins, flavonoids, polyphenols, terpenoids, quercetin, kaempferol, and gypenoside, have been found in *M. oleifera* leaves (Kim et al., 2010). There was prior knowledge that terpenoids, flavonoids, alkaloids, quinines, quercetin, and kaempferol have antimalarial properties (Barliana et al., 2014). Additionally, the antioxidant properties of the polyphenol and flavonoids in these extracts may possibly contribute to the antimalarial activity (El Babili et al., 2010). Free heme is extremely toxic to the malaria parasite, and it has been noted that antioxidant activity can limit the synthesis of

hemozoin (Lubbad et al., 2015). The ability to further standardize new artemisinin-based combination therapy as a potential antimalarial combination makes the additive impact of MO leaf extract with artesunate crucial (Pousibet-Puerto et al., 2016).

Antidiabetic activity of *Moringa oleifera*

Studies by Oyedepo (2013), demonstrated that *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract significantly reduced blood sugar levels in both normal and alloxan-induced diabetic rats. The impact of aqueous leaf extract on lipid profile, body weight, glucose, plasma insulin, evaluation of the homeostatic model, and oral glucose tolerance test in insulin-resistant (IR) and type 1 diabetic rat models was investigated in great detail. Streptozotocin (STZ) (55 mg/kg) was administered to type 1 diabetic rats whereas IR animals were given a high-fructose diet. In contrast to STZ-induced diabetic rats, IR rats demonstrated an increase in hyperinsulinemia, hyperglycemia, and body weight. Studies by Manohar et al. (2012) and Yassa et al. (2014) demonstrated that *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract significantly reduced blood sugar levels in both normal and alloxan-induced diabetic rats. The impact of aqueous leaf extract on lipid profile, body weight, glucose, plasma insulin, evaluation of the homeostatic model, and oral glucose tolerance test in insulin-resistant (IR) and type 1 diabetic rat models was investigated in great detail. Streptozotocin (STZ) (55 mg/kg) was administered to type 1 diabetic rats whereas IR animals were given a high-fructose diet. In contrast to STZ-induced diabetic rats, IR rats demonstrated an increase in hyperinsulinemia, hyperglycemia, and body weight.

Relationship between malaria and diabetes

A study by Danquah et al. (2010) found a statistically significant correlation between malaria and diabetes. In Kumasi, Ghana, persons with and without type 2 diabetes were studied to determine the prevalence of malaria infection. The multivariate model revealed that each mmol/L rise in blood glucose raised the probability for *P. falciparum* infection by 5%. It did this by substituting type 2 diabetes mellitus with glucose concentration. This demonstrated that under various circumstances, an elevated risk for *P. falciparum* infection in individuals with diabetes mellitus could become clinically relevant (and microscopically detectable). On the other hand, kids with more severe type 1 diabetes mellitus who lack semi-immunity may be more susceptible to malaria. This vulnerability is also possible in pregnant women with gestational diabetes, whose immune systems are relatively unprepared to fight off *P. falciparum* during pregnancy (Fried et al., 1998). Additionally, in regions where malaria is widespread, low-level infections in people with type 2 biguanides' antimalarial activity is consistent with the decreased *P. falciparum* prevalence with metformin treatment (Jones et al., 2002).

Conclusion

The major objective of this review was to explore the antimalarial and antidiabetic potency of *Moringa oleifera*; clinical investigations revealed that the leaf extract of MO exhibit significant antimalarial and antidiabetic activities. Therefore, MO leaves can be recommended in combination with artesunate for the treatment of malarial as the combination shows a higher potency compared to the individuals due to the presence of terpenoids, flavonoids, alkaloids, quinines, quercetin, and kaempferol. Similarly, MO leaves can be recommended for the treatment of diabetes as a result of the presence of Glucomoringin, phenols, flavonoids, quercetin-3-glucoside, fiber, and phenol. In addition, a significant relationship was found between diabetes and malaria. This suggests that, there is a decreased immunity hence, low resistance of diabetic individuals to malarial parasites most commonly *Plasmodium falciparum*. For that matter, if the effects of diabetes on infected individuals can be reduced, malarial infection can automatically be mitigated. Despite the significant antimalarial and antidiabetic activities of MO, the mechanism of action by which the MO inhibits the malarial parasites and glucose producing enzymes has not been well elucidated. This therefore calls for further investigation into this topic.

Compliance with ethical standards

No aspect of the work covered in this manuscript involved animal or human patients and no part of this manuscript has been already published elsewhere by any author.

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Conflict of interest

There are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication.

Informed consent

I have given due consideration to the protection of intellectual property associated with this work and that there are no impediments to publication, including the timing of publication, with respect to intellectual property.

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